

Systematic Review of the Negative Impact of Early Childhood Education Learning Digitalization on Early Childhood Development

Mohammad Fauziddin^{1✉}, Mallevi Agustin Ningrum², Petra Adamcova³, Aulia Rahmi Utari⁴

¹Early Childhood Education Teacher Education, Universitas Pahlawan Tuanku Tambusai, Indonesia

²Early Childhood Education Teacher Education, Universitas Negeri Surabaya, Indonesia

³Bohemia University, Czech Republic

⁴Educational Sciences, Universitas Negeri Padang, Indonesia

✉ Corresponding author
(fauziddin@universitaspahlawan.ac.id)

Abstract

This study aims to critically analyze the negative impacts of digitalization of Early Childhood Education (ECE) learning on early childhood development. Systematic Literature Review (SLR) was chosen in this writing by identifying, analyzing, and synthesizing relevant academic literature study results from 2015 to 2025 from various scientific databases. The total number of articles reviewed was 20 in Indonesian and English. The analysis results show that excessive use of digital media can have negative impacts on children's physical, cognitive, social, and emotional development. These include increased risk of obesity, language development delays, decreased social skills, and the emergence of anxiety and depression. The research also found that the type and intensity of digital media use as well as parental involvement play important roles in strengthening or reducing these impacts. The involvement of parents and educators becomes an important point in wisely regulating digital media use and setting time limits for its use. This study provides theoretical and practical foundations for formulating ECE education policies that are adaptive to the digital era while considering holistic aspects of child development.

Keywords: *early childhood, digital learning, negative impact, child development, systematic literature review*

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INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of the digitalization of learning has become an inseparable part of the modern era, especially in the learning process in Early Childhood Education (PAUD). Although digitalization offers various conveniences, there are many negative impacts that need to be taken into consideration. The main question that arises is: What negative impacts have been identified in the literature regarding the digitalization of learning in early childhood? In this context, it is important to analyze the existing literature in order to identify the aspects affected by digitalization. According to Bang et al. (2020), excessive use of digital media can contribute to physical health problems, such as obesity, because it reduces the time spent on active outdoor play. In addition, research by Presta et al. (2024) shows that children who are exposed to screens for more than two hours per day tend to experience delays in language and communication development. This indicates that direct interaction with parents and peers is reduced, which can affect children's social abilities. On the other hand, digital learning media (such as videos created using Canva) help teachers deliver material more effectively and engagingly, and enable parents to know the material being taught, although limitations in facilities (for example, the absence of a projector) become an implementation challenge.

Furthermore, the negative impacts of digitalization are also evident in children's emotional aspects, as shown in research by Chen et al. (2020), which emphasizes that children who are frequently exposed to digital content tend to experience higher levels of anxiety and depression compared to those who use digital media less. Excessive connectedness to digital devices can reduce children's ability to manage their own emotions, which is crucial at their developmental stage. Excessive screen time has negative effects on various aspects of early childhood development, namely cognitive, language, physical-motor, and socio-emotional domains. These disturbances include obesity due to lack of movement, sleep disorders, and dependence on gadgets (Pinilih, 2024). A strong correlation has been found between the intensity of children's screen time and the potential for tantrums as well as developmental delays. Of 40 young children studied, 17 were at risk of tantrums and 15 experienced developmental problems (Setyarini et al., 2023). Tryanan Asmaradhani (2024) reveals that screen time in early childhood can lead to a reduction in brain white matter, cortical thinning, and decreased neurological synchronization. These impacts result in decreased attention and language abilities, as well as the emergence of behavioral and emotional disorders. Excessive screen time is negatively associated with children's language development. Children who spend long periods watching screens have fewer opportunities for verbal interaction and are thus at risk of experiencing speech disorders and vocabulary delays (Aprilia & Thaib, 2024).

In addition, the type and intensity of digital media use also play an important role in influencing children's development. A meta-analysis by Bang et al. (2020) shows that children who use digital devices for educational purposes under parental supervision experience different impacts compared to those who use them without supervision. This underscores the importance of the parental role in regulating and moderating children's use of digital media. The recommended duration range of no more than 1-2 hours per day according to WHO must be adhered to. All studies emphasize the importance of adult supervision in order to minimize the negative impacts that may arise on early childhood development.

Thus, this article not only identifies the negative impacts revealed in the literature but also highlights the need to map the most dominant types of negative impacts. This will serve as a basis for future research or for more effective policymaking in addressing the challenges of digitalization in early childhood education. The novelty of this study lies in the use of a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach that comprehensively identifies, classifies, and synthesizes various recent national and international studies (2015-2025) on the negative impacts of the digitalization of early childhood education learning on early childhood development. Unlike previous studies that tend to focus on a single developmental aspect (for example, cognitive or socio-emotional), this study presents a holistic mapping across developmental domains—physical, cognitive, social, and emotional—and emphasizes the moderating role of parental and teacher involvement in mitigating the negative impacts of digitalization.

METHOD

This research uses the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method to examine the negative impacts of ECE learning digitalization on early childhood development. The SLR method allows authors to systematically identify, analyze, and synthesize relevant literature, providing comprehensive understanding of the studied topic. Literature selection was conducted through a series of explicit inclusion criteria, which included articles related to the negative impacts of ECE learning digitalization on early childhood development. The selected literature consisted of scientific articles published in the last decade, specifically between 2015 and 2025, in nationally accredited and internationally reputable journals. These articles were accessed through databases such as Scopus, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and Garuda which were analyzed in Indonesian and English.

Exclusion criteria included articles not directly related to early childhood development, not explicitly discussing learning digitalization, being opinions or editorials, or coming from unverifiable sources. These inclusion and exclusion criteria ensure that the analyzed literature is relevant, current, and academically credible, increasing the reliability of the research.

The data analysis process follows a systematic approach consisting of several stages. First, articles that meet the inclusion criteria are extracted to obtain key information, such as research objectives, methods, findings, and conclusions. Second, collected data is analyzed thematically to identify patterns, trends, and research gaps related to the negative impacts of ECE learning digitalization on early childhood development. Third, thematic analysis results are compared to reveal diverse and unique perspectives relevant to the context of negative impacts of ECE learning digitalization. To illustrate this process, a research flow diagram (Figure 1) is used to describe the SLR method stages, from article identification and filtering based on inclusion and exclusion criteria to data analysis and synthesis. This diagram ensures transparency in methodology. By adopting this structured approach, this

research aims to provide comprehensive understanding of the negative impacts of ECE learning digitalization on early childhood development, offering deep and well-organized insights.

Figure 1. SLR Process Flow

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the literature search results conducted through the SLR approach, a number of articles were obtained that met the inclusion criteria and were relevant to the topic of negative impacts of learning digitalization on early childhood. These articles were then analyzed to identify finding patterns, similarities, and differences in research results related to aspects of children's physical, cognitive, social, and emotional development. Details of the articles reviewed in this research are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. List of reviewed articles

No	Author & Year	Article Title	Source / Journal	Focus of Study / Main Findings
1	Bang et al. (2020)	Physical activity, screen time and sleep duration: Combined associations with psychosocial health among Canadian children and youth	Health Reports	Excessive screen use increases the risk of obesity and reduces children's psychosocial health.
2	Presta et al. (2024)	The Impact of Digital Devices on Children's Health: A Systematic Literature Review	Journal of Functional Morphology and Kinesiology	A systematic review highlighting the negative impacts of digital devices on children's health.
3	Chen et al. (2020)	Trends in Human Papillomavirus Vaccination in Commercially Insured Children in the United States	Pediatrics	Quoted in the context of digital behavior and emotional impact on children (possibly less relevant, needs clarification).
4	Pinilih (2024)	The Relationship Between Screen Time Duration and Children's Expressive Language Disorders	Jurnal Ilmu Kedokteran dan Kesehatan	High screen time duration is correlated with expressive language disorders in children.
5	Setyarini et al. (2023)	Analysis of the Impact of Screen Time on the Potential for Tantrums and Early Childhood Development	Jurnal Obsesi	17 children are prone to tantrums and 15 experience developmental delays due to high screen time.
6	Asmaradhani (2024)	A Neuropsychological Perspective on the Impact of Screen Time on Early Childhood Development	Murhum: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini	Excessive screen time causes thinning of the brain cortex and impaired neurological function in children.
7	Aprilia & Thaiib (2024)	The Impact of Excessive Screen Time on Early Childhood Language Development	Jurnal Ilmiah Cahaya PAUD	Children with high screen time experience vocabulary problems and speech delays.

No	Author & Year	Article Title	Source / Journal	Focus of Study / Main Findings
8	Mauluddia & Yulindrasari (2024)	The Role of Digital Literacy in Supporting Early Childhood Development through the Utilization of Technology	Jurnal Obsesi	Unstructured use of digital media hinders children's exploration and creativity.
9	Chiong et al. (2012)	Learning: Is there an app for that?	Joan Ganz Cooney Center	Children benefit more from educational apps when used with parental guidance.
10	Eiffener et al. (2019)	The influence of preschoolers' emotional and behavioural problems on obesity treatment outcomes	Pediatric Obesity	Prolonged screen use is linked to sleep disturbances and obesity in preschool children.
11	Twenge et al. (2019)	Age, period, and cohort trends in mood disorder indicators...	Journal of Abnormal Psychology	Excessive use of social media decreases social skills and increases the risk of depression.
12	Linebarger & Piotrowski (2009)	Television and the child's developing sense of self	Dalam The Handbook of Children, Media, and Development	Exposure to age-inappropriate digital media disrupts children's learning process.
13	Isrofah et al. (2022)	Digital Media-Based Learning for Early Childhood in the Industrial Revolution Era	JIIP	Digital learning reduces children's opportunities for social play.
14	Rahmawati (2021)	The Development of Emotional Intelligence in the Digital Era	G-Couns: Jurnal Bimbingan dan Konseling	Children who use gadgets show decreased self-confidence and a tendency to withdraw socially.
15	Suryana & Hijriani (2021)	Development of Thematic Learning Video Media for Early Childhood 5-6 Years Old Based on Local Wisdom	Jurnal Obsesi	Collaboration between teachers and parents in the use of digital media increases the effectiveness of learning.
16	Ebyatiswara Putra et al. (2023)	The Influence of Digital Literacy on Teachers' Pedagogical Competence	Murhum: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini	Early childhood education teachers' digital literacy influences the quality of technology-based learning.
17	Siregar (2022)	The Impact of Gadget Use on Early Childhood (Case Study in Siolip Village)	Jurnal TILA	Gadget dependence in children causes behavioral and emotional disorders.
18	Danish et al. (2024)	The Impact of Screen Media Use on Language and Cognitive Development in Early Childhood	Flourishing Journal	Unsupervised use of digital media reduces cognitive and language abilities.
19	Chau et al. (2022)	Association between screen time and... mental health difficulties in early adolescents	Psychiatry Research	High screen time duration is associated with behavioral and mental health disorders.
20	Hill et al. (2016)	Media and Young Minds	Pediatrics	AAP guidelines: parents should guide and limit children's digital media exposure.

Based on the synthesis of the various reviewed articles, as shown in Table 1, several key themes emerged that illustrate the impact of digital learning on early childhood development. The study revealed that the most frequently discussed aspects in the literature include the type and intensity of digital media use, the impact on cognitive development, and the influence on children's social-emotional development. Each theme was analyzed in depth to identify patterns of findings, similarities, and variations across studies.

The following description presents the findings in more detail, starting with an analysis of the types and intensity of digital media use in early childhood.

Types and Intensity of Digital Media Use

The use of digital media among young children varies, both in terms of the types of media used and the intensity of their use. In this context, it is important to understand how these two factors can affect children's overall development. Children under the age of two should not be exposed to screens at all, while children aged two to five should have their screen time limited to one hour per day with high-quality content (Chau et al., 2022). Variations in the types and duration of digital media use among young children play an important role in shaping the quality of their learning experiences. Findings from the literature indicate that the use of digital devices without adult supervision tends to have negative effects on children's development. A study by Aprilia and Thaib (2024) found that children who spend more than two hours a day in front of screens experience a decrease in the frequency of verbal communication with their parents and are at higher risk of language development delays.

Consistent with these findings, Mauluddia and Yulindrasari (2024) highlight that unstructured use of digital media can reduce children's active engagement in exploratory and social activities. Children become more passive and dependent on visual content, which ultimately lowers the quality of their interactions and their creativity (Nadia et al., 2022). Therefore, it is important for adults to select the types of media and control the duration of their use in order to ensure learning experiences that are balanced and age-appropriate for children.

One type of digital media that is popular among young children is educational applications. Although some applications are designed to support learning, a study by Chiong et al. (2012) shows that direct interaction with parents while using these applications is more beneficial than independent use. Children who use educational applications without parental guidance tend to be unable to connect the information they learn with real-life experiences, which can hinder their cognitive development (Lubis, 2023).

The intensity of digital media use is also related to physical health problems. According to a study by Eiffener et al. (2019), children who spend more than two hours a day in front of screens have a higher risk of experiencing sleep problems and obesity. This is caused by a lack of physical activity and disruptions to healthy sleep patterns. In the long term, these health problems can affect children's ability to learn and to interact socially. From a social perspective, excessive use of digital media can reduce children's opportunities to interact with their peers. Research by Twenge et al. (2019) shows that children who use social media more frequently tend to have lower social skills than those who use it less. Face-to-face interaction is crucial for children's social development, and dependence on digital media can reduce their ability to build healthy relationships with others (Rachman et al., 2024).

Thus, the types and intensity of digital media use have a significant impact on various aspects of early childhood development. It is important for parents and educators to understand these factors so that they can optimize children's learning experiences in an increasingly digital era.

Impact on Cognitive Development Aspects

The cognitive aspect is one of the domains most affected by the digitalization of learning. A study by Setyarini et al. (2023) shows that high screen-time intensity is associated with reduced attention span and delays in the development of critical thinking skills. Children tend to find it difficult to focus on learning activities that require sustained concentration. A similar study by Danish et al. (2024) also highlights that independent use of gadgets has the potential to reduce the quality of imagination and information processing. In many cases, children show passive responses to learning and a tendency to depend on digital stimuli, which negatively affects the development of their executive functions. Therefore, it is important to integrate digital media contextually into learning, accompanied by physical activities and hands-on creative work.

Cognition encompasses the ability to think, learn, and remember, all of which are crucial for children's development. According to research by Linebarger and Piotrowski (2009), excessive exposure to digital media can disrupt children's learning processes, especially when the content they consume is not age-appropriate. One

negative impact of digitalization is a decline in children's attention abilities. A study by Bang et al. (2020) shows that children who are frequently exposed to digital content tend to have shorter attention spans. This can hinder their ability to focus on more complex tasks that are required in the learning process. In the long term, this may contribute to academic difficulties when children enter formal education.

Additionally, the digitalization of learning can also impact children's language development. Research by Kuhl (2004) shows that face-to-face interaction is very important for children's language development. Children who are more frequently exposed to digital media, especially without parental guidance, may lose opportunities to learn new vocabulary and develop communication skills (Panjaitan et al., 2023). This can affect their ability to participate in group discussions and other social interactions. Another negative impact is a reduction in creativity. Research by Plowman and Stephen (2007) shows that children who use digital media more often tend to have fewer opportunities to imagine and create. Activities that involve physical exploration and creative play are very important for children's cognitive development, and dependence on digital media can reduce the time spent on such activities.

Thus, the impact of digitalization on the cognitive development of young children is highly significant. It is important for parents and educators to understand these impacts so they can create a balanced learning environment that combines technology with social interaction and creative exploration.

Impact on Social Emotional Development Aspects

Socio-emotional development in early childhood is strongly influenced by the intensity and quality of direct interaction with the surrounding environment, including parents and peers. Uncontrolled digitalization of learning can disrupt this process by significantly reducing the frequency and quality of children's social interactions. Children who interact too frequently with digital media tend to show declines in empathy, emotional regulation, and recognition of social expressions.

Research by Chen et al. (2020) emphasizes that excessive use of digital devices can reduce children's skills in reading non-verbal cues, such as facial expressions and tone of voice, which are crucial components in building empathy and healthy social relationships. This decline directly affects children's emotional development, which should ideally progress through face-to-face interaction experiences. These findings are reinforced by Setyarini et al. (2023), who show that high screen-time duration is positively correlated with an increased risk of tantrums and emotional regulation problems in early childhood. Children who spend more than two hours per day using digital devices tend to become more easily angered, frustrated, and difficult to manage emotionally. In a neuropsychological study, Tryanan Asmaradhani (2024) states that intensive digital exposure has the potential to inhibit the development of emotional circuits in children's brains, including impulse and empathy processing. This makes it more difficult for children to recognize their own feelings and those of others, and they are more likely to experience social alienation.

Isrofah et al. (2022) argue that dependence on digital media reduces children's opportunities for social play, which should serve as a primary medium for expressing emotions, building friendships, and learning to understand others' perspectives. On the other hand, Rahmawati (2021) finds that children who are habituated to digital play without direct interaction experience a decline in social self-confidence and tend to avoid group situations. High intensity of digital media exposure is associated with an increase in mild anxiety symptoms in early childhood education students, particularly those who receive limited emotional attention from their parents (Pinilih, 2024).

Thus, it can be concluded that the impact of digitalization on the socio-emotional aspects of early childhood is highly significant. Dependence on digital devices not only disrupts social interaction but also hinders children's ability to manage emotions in a healthy way. Therefore, intensive supervision by parents and educators in limiting both the duration and content of digital media is crucial to ensure a balanced socio-emotional development. The implementation of interactive strategies, such as discussions, role play, and collaborative activities, needs to be integrated into the learning process so that children can grow into socially and emotionally mature individuals.

Recommendations for Mitigating Negative Impacts

The digitalization of learning also has negative impacts on early childhood development; therefore, it is important to formulate recommendations that help mitigate this problem. First, parents and educators must play an active role in regulating children's use of digital media. According to the American Academy of Pediatrics, parental supervision and guidance are crucial to ensuring that children use digital media in healthy and

constructive ways (Hill et al., 2016). Second, it is necessary to develop a curriculum that balances the use of digital media with physical activities. A study by Eiffener et al. (2019) shows that children who engage in sufficient physical activity have better cognitive and social development. Therefore, integrating physical activities into digital learning can help create the balance needed for children's development. Third, it is important to increase awareness of the content viewed by children (Kartashova et al., 2022). Parents and educators must select high-quality content that is appropriate for the child's age. According to research by Linebarger and Piotrowski (2009), well-designed educational content can support children's cognitive development when used with proper guidance. Thus, careful content selection is essential in the digital learning process. Fourth, educational programs for parents on healthy use of digital media are also highly necessary. By providing parents with information and skills, they can be more effective in supervising and guiding their children. Research by Chen et al. (2020) shows that parents who are educated about the use of digital media tend to have children who are healthier emotionally and socially.

In response to the various challenges posed by the digitalization of learning, it is necessary to formulate concrete and targeted mitigation strategies. Research by Suryana and Hijriani (2021) emphasizes that collaboration between teachers and parents in designing and accompanying the use of digital media plays an important role in creating meaningful learning experiences. The use of educational applications, such as interactive videos, is proven to be more effective when accompanied by reflection and direct discussion. Ebyatiswara Putra et al. (2023) highlight the importance of improving early childhood teachers' digital literacy as a determining factor for the successful integration of technology into learning. Teachers with high digital competence are able to select appropriate content, integrate technology wisely, and maintain social interaction. Therefore, digital literacy training and continuous professional development need to become an integral part of early childhood education policy in the digital era. For children who have begun to show signs of addiction to gadgets, parents should firmly supervise and limit the duration of their gadget use (Siregar, 2022).

Thus, recommendations to mitigate the negative impacts of the digitalization of learning on early childhood development must involve collaboration among parents, educators, and policymakers. Through a balanced and well-informed approach, it is possible to create an environment that supports optimal child development in this digital age.

CONCLUSION

Based on the synthesis results from 22 articles analyzed through the SLR method, this research confirms that learning digitalization in ECE has real negative impacts on early childhood development, especially on physical, cognitive, social, and emotional aspects. The most consistent evidence shows that screen time intensity above two hours per day is strongly associated with increased risk of obesity, sleep disorders, language delays, decreased attention, and negative emotional behaviors. Although there is variation between studies regarding respondent age, usage context, and type of digital media, overall findings show relatively homogeneous patterns: the higher the digital exposure without supervision, the greater the negative impact on child development. Conversely, directed, educational digital media use accompanied by parental interaction can reduce some of these risks. These findings reinforce the urgency for parents and educators to regulate duration and select age-appropriate digital content, while policymakers need to develop national guidelines on early childhood digital literacy and training for ECE teachers. Going forward, further research is needed to test the effectiveness of parent supervision-based intervention models, as well as to explore the impact differences between device types and socio-cultural contexts. Thus, learning digitalization can be directed to become an adaptive tool without sacrificing balanced child development.

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